

Altmetrics for Brazilian educational journals: Analysis of Educ@ Collection

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Introduction

Journals are one of the main means for disseminating scientific production. However, to qualify them, the responsible instances still favour the use of indexes based on traditional metrics, ignoring a series of thematic specificities, as well as the impact existing outside the academic sphere.

In certain areas of knowledge, such as the humanities, editors lack accurate and reliable information to support their decisions regarding management and editorial policies (Benchimol et al., 2014). In addition to traditional citation indicators, alternative metrics can assist these editors in verifying the online attention that their journal's articles receive on the social web.

This work sought to investigate the alternative impact of articles from Educ@ Collection, a Brazilian open access platform that, implemented in 2010 by Carlos Chagas Foundation (São Paulo), aggregates more than 60 relevant journals in the educational field (<http://educa.fcc.org.br/>).

So far, some studies have been conducted that investigate altmetric applications in the education area, but few of them analyse the impact of altmetrics in journals in this area and none portray the Brazilian context. Most of the studies come from medical and health education fields and seek to correlate altmetric and citation data, whether from a single journal (Amath et al., 2017) or a set (Maggio et al., 2018; Sperka & Phillips, 2022).

Methods

The exploratory study analyzes altmetric data from a set of Brazilian journals present in Educ@ Collection. Only Brazilian journals published in Portuguese (n=55) with publications between 2018 and 2022 were considered.

The articles on the Portal, which are in XML Jats (Journal Article Tag Suite) format, were processed,

and some of their data, such as title of the journal, title of the text, DOI, authorship and references, were extracted through libraries for data manipulation and regular expressions.

We performed queries from the DOIs extracted from the XML Jats through Altmetric API, obtaining files with the altmetric impact data. Then, we registered this data locally in a relational database, in order to guarantee its consistency in relation to the other data extracted from the documents, and later we migrated the information to an index in Elasticsearch. This process intended to increase the speed of queries.

Then, we imported the index into a dashboard creation tool (Superset), which allows us to assemble a series of graphs grouped according to different themes. Within the dashboard referring to the metrics and indicators of Educ@ Collection, we created a panel concerning its altmetric impact.

Results

Of the 55 journals analyzed, 47 (85%) obtained altmetric data with at least one mention in the period. From 12,048 articles published between 2018 and 2022, we could extract 10,115 registered DOIs. Of these, only 711 had altmetric data recorded, indicating low coverage (7%) of the total.

In all, more than 3,180 mentions were registered, distributed in the main sources, in this order: Mendeley (17.8k), Twitter (2.02k), Facebook (334), News and blogs (305) and Wikipedia (118). Figure 1 shows the distribution of each source by the average obtained, and Figure 2 demonstrates the performance of the journals, highlighting the score of the most punctuated articles.

Figure 1. Impact distribution according to altmetric sources (average)

Mendeley and Twitter were also the sources with the best performance compared to others in altmetric studies in the area of medical education and health education (Amath et al., 2017; Maggio et al., 2018). Although Mendeley is not considered in the calculation of the altmetric score, it was the source with the highest performance when compared to the others. The result is similar to that of Maggio et al. (2018) with considerably larger Mendeley bookmarks.

Another similarity with the study is the low coverage of sources such as news and blogs. SciELO's role in disseminating Brazilian articles stands out in its blog SciELO em Perspectiva, which is the main channel of this type of source, concentrating 96% of the posts.

In addition to low coverage in terms of mentions of articles published in the period, the results indicate a low average in the value of the scores of publications, with an average of only 2.87.

The five articles with the highest attention value scored, in this order, 52, 48, 40, 39, and 38. What they have in common is dealing with ethnic-racial themes, gender and inclusion, in the context of education. The results are in line with considerations about the influence of research themes on altmetric performance (Scotti et al., 2020) and on how research with political and social themes has the ability to generate online attention and thus more public engagement with research.

Figure 2. Distribution of article scores among journals

The journals with the best altmetric performance, with summed values, are: *Educação e Pesquisa* (917), *Revista Estudos Feministas* (699), *Ensaio: Avaliação e Políticas Públicas em Educação* (387), *Educação e Realidade* (359), and *Educação em Revista* (127). Even though the *Revista Brasileira de Educação Médica* works with texts from the areas of health education and medical education, it was not among the top 10. It actually appears in 13th position, with a score of only 55. It is necessary to consider, both in this case and in the other journals, recent findings that point to a high concentration of online attention (91%) and higher altmetric values for research in the English language, and much lower performance for other languages (Yu et al., 2018).

Conclusion

We can conclude that, although the Educ@ journals have good altmetric coverage (85%), their articles receive little online attention, obtaining better performance in certain thematic areas. Mendeley and Twitter are the main sources of altmetric data. More studies are needed, in order to investigate the consequences of these findings.

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